

CONDENSATION OF ARYL DIAZONIUM SALTS WITH REACTIVE UNSATURATED COMPOUNDS. PART V*. ACTION OF ARYL DIAZONIUM CHLORIDES WITH BROMOMALEIC ACID

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An aryl diazonium chloride reacts with bromomaleic acid (A) to give a β -arylated product, viz, an α -bromo- β -arylacrylic acid of a certain stereoisomeric form. The non-reversible nature of radical and ionic addition for (A) is confirmed and the occurrence of β -arylation both in (A) and citraconic acid is clarified.

Dhingra and Mathur (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 123) extended the diazo reactions of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compounds (cf. Meerwein *et al.*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, ii, 152, 237; Koelsch *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 412) conducted in the presence of sodium acetate and copper chloride to citraconic acid and mesaconic acid, both representing an unsymmetrical unsaturated system

containing two activating groups. In the cases studied, the aryl diazonium chlorides reacted so as to give an α -methyl- β -arylacrylic acid according to the following procedure:

and as is natural (cf. Koelsch *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, p. 413), when coupling occurs adjacent to a -COOH group, the elements of carbon dioxide were also expelled. The reaction showed that arylation had occurred β to the methyl group, and further, it was also reverse to the ionic mode of addition known for citraconic acid. This reversal could happen, if the diazo reaction had involved radical addition (cf. Ann. Rep. Chemical Society, London, 1948, p. 155).

*In Part IV (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 507) the action of aryl diazonium chlorides was studied on α -methylacrylic acid, whereby α -methylcinnamic acids were obtained. A paper by Fusco and Rossi (*Gazzetta*, 1948, 78, 524) abstracted rather late in the British Abstracts (1951, AII, 413) came to our notice later. By coupling diazotised bases, different from those described in Part IV, with α -methylacrylic acid, they too had got α -methylcinnamic acids. They had used acetone as the solvent. It may be noted, however, that before the appearance of Fusco and Rossi's paper, the principle that the interaction of diazo salts with maleic acid and acrylic acid type of compounds would give cinnamic acid derivatives had already been worked out in the studies earlier in this series.

a fact which has been substantiated by comparing the acid with an authentic sample of *cis-p*-chloro- α -bromocinnamic acid. Reactions made with *m*-chloro- and *o*-chlorobenzene diazonium chlorides also indicate the formation of the *cis-z*-bromocinnamic acids. However, similar reaction with *p*-bromobenzene diazonium chloride yields a mixture of *cis*- and *trans-p*-bromo- α -bromocinnamic acids.

In one experiment with *p*-nitrobenzene diazonium chloride, the evolved gases have been observed to contain carbon dioxide. As in no case there is found evidence for the formation of β -bromo- β -arylacrylic acid, the reaction occurring between aryl diazonium chlorides and bromomaleic acid may be formulated as under :

the arylation occurring at the β -position. These acids cannot have resulted after spontaneous dehalogenation of an adduct, e. g.,

in the final stages of the reaction. In that event some α -chlorocinnamic acids should also have been present in the reaction mixtures. They appear to be formed directly as shown in the equation.

It is clear, however, that, unlike cinnamic acid, bromomaleic acid is a genuine case in whose reactions ionic and radical addition cause no reversal. Recalling also the results obtained with citraconic acid, it is evident that in both cases (I, X = -COOH; R = Br & -CH₃) the intermediate radical first formed is (II A)

(which is more stable than IIb). But, with two substituents opposite in their electrical effects (Br : -I, + M ; -CH₃ : + I), it is difficult to see how application of Koelsch's

concept of the ease of resonance (*loc. cit.*, p. 413) can explain the greater stability of (IIa) in both cases. The same difficulty is there with regard to radical addition known for bromoethylene (vinyl bromide) and propylene (I, X=H, R=Br & -CH₃). Based on his new concept, Barton (*Nature*, 1948, 162, 182), however, has shown that in the last two cases, the carbon atom 2 should be the seat of radical attack as, referred to the symmetrical molecule ethylene (I, X=H, R=H), it has the greatest differential electron density. Considering that in the acids (I, X=-COOH, R=Br & -CH₃) the two COOH groups (-I, -M), would tend to cause the same depletion of electrons at carbon atoms 1 and 2, it can similarly be justified that the carbon atom 2 in both of these acids will still be left with highest differential electron density, and therefore amenable to radical attack.

The precise factors which govern the formation of a particular stereoisomeric cinnamic acid are being further studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromomaleic acid (m.p. 141°) was prepared by Walden's method (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2886). The dibromosuccinic acid needed for this preparation was efficiently obtained by the bromination of sodium fumarate (vide Eichelberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 1321). Employing Naar's method (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 250; for proof of configuration cf. Reich and Chang, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 235) the *trans*-*o*-nitro- α -bromocinnamic acid of m.p. 208° (lit., m.p. 211°) and *trans*-*p*-nitro α -bromocinnamic acid of m.p. 206° were obtained by the oxidation of *o*- and *p*-nitro- α -bromocinnamic aldehydes, m.p. 96° and 136° respectively. The latter two were obtained together by the nitration of α -bromocinnamic aldehyde which in turn was obtainable from cinnamic aldehyde (cf. Zincke and Hagen, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1814). The mixture of the nitro-aldehydes could also be separated by steam distillation, when the *o*-isomer came over in the steam distillate much more readily than the *p*-isomer. The crude aldehydes could then be further purified in the usual manner. The *cis*-*p*-chloro- α -bromocinnamic acid (m.p. 129°), also needed for comparison, was obtained from *p*-chloro- α - β -dibromodihydrocinnamic acid (m.p. 187°) according to the method of Reich *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 793).

In the acids synthesised, the extra-nuclear (labile) bromine was estimated by dehalogenating a sample by heating it with 10% aqueous caustic soda (25 c. c.) for 2 to 3 hours and determining the liberated bromine by Volhard's method. The dehalogenation was quantitative.

All the experiments were done in the absence of acetone (vide Kai and Mathur, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 383).

Condensation of p-, m- and o-Nitrobenzene and α - and β -Naphthalene Diazonium Chlorides with Bromomaleic Acid.—*p*-Nitroaniline (3.45 g., *M*/40) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (conc., 6 c. c., 2.5 times the base) and water (10 c. c.) with a little warming. The solution was then suddenly cooled by addition of crushed ice (3.4 g.). To the hydrochloride, precipitated in the form of fine crystals, was added an ice-cold

solution of 87% sodium nitrite (2.1 g., *M/40*) in water (7 c. c.) all at once. The diazotised base was filtered through glass wool and the filtrate added directly into a solution of bromomaleic acid (4.82 g., *M/40*), sodium acetate (5.75 g.) and copper chloride (1 g.) in water (20 c. c.). The reaction mixture was stirred and warmed to 30°-35°. There was a brisk effervescence in the beginning which could continue for a long time (2 days). However, after keeping overnight, the mixture was filtered and the residue treated with 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10-15 c. c.) with a little warming. The sodium bicarbonate extract upon acidification gave an acid, which after trituration with benzene, crystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 207°. According to Naar (*loc. cit.*) *trans-p*-nitro- α -bromocinnamic acid has m.p. 206°. (Found: Br, 29.33; equiv., 271. $C_9H_7O_4NBr$ requires Br, 29.07 per cent. Equiv., 272). It gave an ethyl ester, m.p. 94°. Ethyl *trans-p*-nitro- α -bromocinnamate has m. p. 94-94.5° (*vide Pfeiffer, Ber., 1914, 47, 1769*). Mixed m. p. of the nitro-acid with a sample prepared by Naar's method (*vide supra*) 207°, yield 0.937 g. (15%). It was observed, however, that on allowing the effervescence to go on for a longer time the yield was somewhat better.

In a similar experiment, with twice the amount of material the evolved gases were scrubbed through dilute hydrochloric acid and were led through baryta water, when a milkiness was produced, showing the presence of CO_2 .

Experiments were done also with *m*- and *o*-nitroanilines and α - and β -naphthylamines, but the last three amines required acetic acid as a solvent during diazotisation. All of them finally gave *trans*-acids. The results, which for the sake of comparison include those of the *p*-nitroaniline as well, are recorded in the following table.

TABLE I

Amine diazotised (with AcOH, if necessary)	Yield.		M. p. & appearance.		% Bromine.		Equivalent.	
			Observed	Expected	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline (3.45 g.)	0.937 g.	15%	Needles (H_2O), m.p. & mixed m.p. 207°. Ethyl ester, m.p. 94°	Needles (H_2O), m.p. 206°. Ethyl ester, m.p. 94° (<i>vide supra</i>)	29.33	29.07	271	272
<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline (3.45 g.)	1.40	21	Needles (benzene), m. p. 217-18°. Ethyl ester, m. p. 74°.	Needles* (benzene), m. p. 217-18° Ethyl ester** m. p. 74°	29.10	29.07	275	272
<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline (3.45 g., AcOH 15 c. c.)	0.24	5	Needles (H_2O), m. p. 208°; mixed m. p. 208°.	Needles (H_2O), m. p. 208 (<i>vide supra</i>)	29.23	29.07	276	272
α -Naphthylamine (AcOH, 7 c. c.)	0.33	4	Fine needles (dil. alcohol), m. p. 152°.	---	29.00	28.90	265	277
β -Naphthylamine (AcOH, 7 c. c.)	0.25	3	Needles (H_2O), m. p. 162-65° (impure)	---	34.92	28.90	259.1	277

* Reich and Koehler, *Ber., 1913, 46, 3733*.

** Wollering, *Ber., 1914, 47, 110*.

Condensations of p-, m- and o-Chlorobenzene Diazonium Chlorides with Bromomaleic Acid.—The *p*-chloroaniline (3.2 g., *M/40*) was diazotised and then condensed with bromomaleic acid (4.82 g., *M/40*) as in the case of *p*-nitroaniline. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residue treated with 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10-15 c. c.). The bicarbonate extract was filtered, the filtrate and washings were acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid when an acid was precipitated. It was filtered, washed with water and dried and then crystallised from petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 129°. According to Reich *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), *cis-p*-chloro- α -bromocinnamic acid has m.p. 129°. (Found: Br, 29.3; equiv., 260.2. $C_9H_7O_2ClBr$ requires Br, 30.65 per cent. Equiv., 261.5). Mixed m.p. of the acid with the authentic *cis-p*-chloro- α -bromocinnamic acid was 129°, yield 1.35 g. (20%). Refluxing the acid in carbon disulphide with 2 to 3 drops of bromine raised the m.p. of the acid to 200°. Reich *et al.* by doing the refluxing in chloroform solution claimed for the *trans-p*-chloro- α -bromocinnamic acid a m. p. 256°, which could not be attained in carbon disulphide solution.

Experiments were repeated with *m*-chloro- and *o*-chlorobenzene diazonium chlorides when also *cis*-cinnamic acids were obtained. The results, which include those from the *p*-chloroaniline again, are recorded below.

TABLE II

cis- α -Bromocinnamic acid.

Amine diazotised (3.2 g., <i>M/40</i>)	Yield.	M p. & appearance.		% Bromine.		Equivalent.	
		Observed.	Expected†	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	1.35 g. 20%	Needles (pet. ether), m.p. & mixed m.p. 129°	Needles (pet. ether) m.p. 129° (<i>vide supra</i>)	29.3	30.65	260.2	261.5
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	1.34 20	Crystals (abs. alc. + CS ₂), m.p. *87° Refluxing (6hrs) in pet. ether + Br ₂ (2 drops) raised m.p. to 137°.	Needles (dil. AcOH or pet. ether), m.p. 100°. Trans isomer, m.p. 140°.	31.34	30.65	259.7	261.5
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	0.73 11	Long needles (H ₂ O), m.p. 125°.	Long needles (hot H ₂ O), m.p. 128°.	30.10	30.65	254.6	261.5

* sample appeared to be contaminated with the *trans*-isomer. In fact its m.p., though low in the beginning, rose considerably on keeping.

† *Vide Reich et al., loc. cit.*

Condensation of p-Bromobenzene Diazonium Chloride with Bromomaleic Acid in the presence of Copper Chloride and Sodium Acetate.—The diazotised amine (4.3 g., *M/40*) was condensed with bromomaleic acid (*M/40*) as in the case of *p*-nitroaniline. Effervescence, which was quick in the beginning, continued* for over two days. Aqueous

sodium bicarbonate extracted from the solid formed during the reaction, a mixture of acids, yield 2.1 g. An extract made out of the crude acids with excess of boiling water on cooling deposited needles, and left a residue (R, 1.1 g.). The former had m. p. 147°. [Found: Br (labile), 25.84; equiv, 307.7. $C_9H_6O_2Br_2$ requires Br (labile), 26.1 per cent. Equiv., 306]. The residue (R) was recrystallised twice from dilute alcohol (1:4) giving mostly another acid, m. p. 216°. (Found: Equiv., 305. $C_9H_6O_2Br_2$ requires equiv., 306]. However, in working the residue (R), a very small amount of a material relatively less soluble in dilute alcohol was also isolated, but it could not be identified. The acids of m.p. 147° and 216° appeared to be *cis-trans* isomerides. This was confirmed in the following way (cf. Reich *et al.* for the *p*-chloro analogue).

The acid of m.p. 147° (0.2 g.) was refluxed with chloroform (30 c.c.) containing bromine (2-3 drops) for 1½ hours. Afterwards, the chloroform was distilled over. The residue was recrystallised from dilute alcohol (1:4) in needles, m.p. 217°. [Found: Br (labile), 25.63; equiv., 307. $C_9H_6O_2Br_2$ requires Br (labile), 26.1 per cent. Equiv., 306]. Mixed m. p. with the acid from the residue (R), 216°.

It is significant to note that *p*-chlorobenzene diazonium chloride did not yield with dibromomaleic acid, the known *cis*- or *trans*-*p*-chloro- $\alpha\beta$ -dibromomaleic acids, but rather a very small amount of an unidentifiable, low melting acid of m.p. 92-95°. In all the experiments described above, there was invariably found a considerable amount of non-acidic matter present in the reaction mixture.

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